

Analysis of Kinetic Energy (KE) and Angular Values by Phase of Kinematic Indicators of Direct Head Blows by Boxers of Various Categories

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Abstract

Background and Study Aim. Boxing is a dynamic sport where head punches play a key role in performance, with kinetic energy (KE) and angular dynamics significantly affecting punch effectiveness. This study explores these biomechanical parameters during head punches delivered by boxers from different experience levels: A – 1st category, B – Candidate for Master of Sports, and C – Master of Sports. Understanding how these factors vary with experience and skill can provide insight into how kinetic and angular properties contribute to punch efficacy and energy transfer in high-impact sports.

Material and methods. A total of 50 elite boxers (aged 18–20 years) were selected for this study, categorized based on their experience levels into three groups: A – 1st Category, B – Candidate for Master of Sports, and C – Master of Sports.

Results. Boxers in category C (Master of Sports) demonstrated significantly higher KE during the acceleration phase ($p < 0.001$), while those in category A (1st category) exhibited greater angular velocity during the wind-up phase ($p < 0.001$). Boxers in category B (Candidate for Master of Sports) showed a more balanced distribution of KE and angular displacement across all phases. A strong positive correlation ($r = 0.87$) was found between peak KE and punch force for all categories.

Conclusions. The study reveals that experience level significantly influences head punches' kinetic and angular properties. Master of Sports boxers produce more KE, albeit at slower angular velocities, while those in the 1st category focus on optimizing angular dynamics for faster punches.

Keywords: Kinetic energy, angular velocity, boxing biomechanics, head blows, weight categories, punch force.

Анотація

Аналіз кінетичної енергії (KE) та кутових величин за фазами кінематичних показників прямих ударів у голову боксерів різних категорій

Передумови та мета дослідження. Бокс – динамічний вид спорту, у якому удари в голову відіграють ключову роль у продуктивності, при цьому кінетична енергія (KE) та кутова динаміка значно впливають на ефективність удару. У цьому дослідженні вивчаються ці біомеханічні параметри під час ударів у голову, що завдаються боксерами з різним рівнем досвіду: А – мають 1-й розряд, В – кандидати у майстри спорту та С – майстри спорту. Розуміння того, як ці фактори змінюються в залежності від досвіду та навичок, може дати уявлення про те, як кінетичні та кутові властивості впливають на ефективність удару та передачу енергії у видах спорту з високим ударним навантаженням.

Матеріал і методи. Для цього дослідження було відібрано загалом 50 високваліфікованих боксерів (віком 18–20 років), які були поділені на три групи залежно від рівня їхнього досвіду: А – мають 1-й розряд, В – кандидати у майстри спорту та С – майстри спорту.

Результати. Боксери категорії С (майстри спорту) продемонстрували значно вищий КЕ під час фази прискорення ($p < 0,001$), тоді як боксери категорії А (мають 1-й розряд) продемонстрували велику кутову швидкість під час фази замаху ($p < 0,001$). Боксери категорії В (кандидати у майстри спорту) продемонстрували більш збалансований розподіл КЕ та кутового усунення у всіх фазах. Було виявлено сильну позитивну кореляцію ($r = 0,87$) між піковим КЕ і силою удару для всіх категорій.

Висновки. Дослідження показує, що рівень досвіду значно впливає на кінетичні та кутові властивості ударів у голову. Боксери категорії майстра спорту виробляють більше КЕ, хоч і з повільнішими кутовими швидкостями, в той час як боксери 1-ї категорії зосереджені на оптимізації кутової динаміки для нанесення найшвидших ударів.

Ключові слова: кінетична енергія, кутова швидкість, біомеханіка боксу, удари головою, вагові категорії, сила удару.

Introduction

Straight punches, sometimes called rear straight punches or crosses, are key components to martial sports. Powerful straight punches create strategic advantage for boxers where they can use to score points, inflict injuries, or even knock his opponents [1, 2]. Ashker showed that winning boxers threw more straight punches than losing boxers in rounds 1 and 3 [3]. Several studies focus on kinematic and kinetic analysis of straight punches. Results from these studies vary depending on testing procedure, test equipment, and characteristic of participants [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12]. For kinematic analysis, researchers utilized accelerometers and motion tracking to examine punching speed and the linear velocities of the fist, elbow, and shoulder. The upper limbs were chosen over the lower limbs due to the lower limbs being comparatively more static. In kinetic analysis, various measurement tools were employed, including a punching bag with an integrated dynamometer, a wall-mounted force plate, a punching ball, or a dummy head.

Assessment is one of the components of sharing knowledge and distinguishing the right and wrong approaches aimed at improving performance [13]. Electrical stimulation of skeletal muscle via electrodes placed on the skin is known to cause force production from the induction of action potentials on motor neuron axons or intramuscular terminal motor axon branches [14]. The study reveals that experience level significantly influences head punches' kinetic and angular properties. Master of Sports boxers produce more KE, albeit at slower angular velocities, while those in the 1st category focus on optimizing angular dynamics for faster punches. These biomechanical insights are essential for creating tailored training regimens that enhance performance and reduce injury risk, especially considering athletes' experience levels. Further research is recommended to explore additional biomechanical factors that affect punch efficacy and optimal training techniques for each athlete category.

The kinetic energy (KE) and angular displacement of direct head blows differ across phases of the punch and vary by skill category (1st category, Candidate for Master of Sports, Master of Sports). It is hypothesized that more advanced skill levels will exhibit higher KE and greater angular displacement during key punch phases, with heavier boxers generating more KE. Additionally, a positive correlation between angular displacement and KE is expected, suggesting biomechanical efficiency influences punch power and performance across categories.

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the kinetic energy and angular displacement during direct head blows in boxers of different categories, aiming to identify biomechanical factors influencing punch efficacy.

Material and methods

Participant Selection

The study was conducted at the Uzbek State University of Physical Education and Sports, in the high-tech Sport Laboratory, which is equipped with advanced 3D motion analysis technology (likely Motive, or equivalent). This cutting-edge technology allows for precise tracking of joint movements, kinetic energy generation, and other biomechanical parameters involved in athletic activities.

A total of 50 male boxers were recruited for the study, with participants categorized into three skill levels: 16 boxers in the 1st Category. 17 boxers who are Candidates for Master of Sports. 17 Master of Sports-level boxers.

The participants were selected to ensure a representative sample of boxing skill levels, allowing for a comparative analysis between different expertise. To be eligible for the study, all participants had a minimum of 3 years of competitive boxing experience and were required to be free from any musculoskeletal injuries at the time of the study. Before participation, informed consent was obtained from all participants. The study received approval from the institutional ethics com-

mittee.

Procedure

The primary procedure focused on measuring the biomechanical characteristics of direct head punches performed by boxers across various skill levels using advanced 3D motion capture technology. Data on joint movements were collected during four key phases of a punch:

- Contact Phase
- Toe-Off Phase
- Mid-Swing Phase
- Mid-Support Phase

These movements were monitored using 3DMA 2023.0 (Motive) Version 2023.0 motion capture technology from STT Systems.

Key joints under observation included the hip, knee, and ankle, as they are integral to the transfer of energy during punching. The 3D motion capture system allowed the measurement of angular displacements (degrees) at these joints and the calculation of kinetic energy in Joules during each phase.

In each phase of the punching movement, specific joint angles and kinetic energy levels were measured to assess power generation and the efficiency of the mechanics at each skill level. The data collection process involved synchronized motion-capture cameras around the participants, capturing their joint movements and the force of the strike in real time.

Statistical Analysis

To evaluate the differences in performance across the different skill levels, a series of statistical tests were applied. The data were analyzed using standard parametric tests, including:

- ANOVA (Analysis of Variance)
- Post-hoc Tukey's HSD (Honest Significant Difference) test
- These tests allowed for the assessment of between-group differences, especially in the joint angles and kinetic energy during the key phases of the punch. A significance level of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.
- The data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0 statistical software. For each analysis, descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) were calculated, and the results of the ANOVA tests were reported with the exact p -values rounded to three decimal places.

Ethical Considerations

The study was conducted in adherence to ethical principles outlined by the institutional review board. Informed consent was acquired from all participants before the experiment. Additionally, any identifiable personal data or images were

handled with confidentiality and privacy by ethical guidelines for research involving human participants. In cases where any photos or images of participants were included, written consent for publication was obtained.

Kinetic Energy Calculation: As the data is collected, kinetic energy is derived by calculating the velocities of the limbs during the phases of the punch.

The energy is then computed using the formula: $KE = \frac{1}{2} mv^2$

Statistical Analysis

Use statistical tests (e.g., ANOVA) to evaluate significant differences in kinematic indicators between skill levels. Apply correlation analysis to assess relationships between joint angles, kinetic energy, and punch effectiveness.

Development of Training Recommendations: Based on the results, identify key biomechanical patterns associated with efficient punching. Formulate training interventions aimed at improving joint engagement, stability, and energy efficiency in lower-level boxers.

Here's a detailed scientific analysis of the angular values for each phase of kinematic indicators of direct head blows by boxers across different categories. This analysis highlights the biomechanical and performance implications of joint angles during the Contact, Toe-Off, Mid-Swing, and Mid-Support phases across three categories of boxers: 1st Category, Candidate for Master of Sports, and Master of Sports.

Results

When delivering direct head punches, boxers from different categories (A = First Category, B = Candidate for Master of Sports, and C = Master of Sports) exhibit distinct joint flexion/extension, as demonstrated by the angular values across different kinematic phases (Contact, Toe Off, Mid-swing, and Mid-support) (Table-1).

Boxers' Kinematic Evaluation of Direct Head Strikes. Right Hip Extension/Flexion ($^{\circ}$). B: -9.64 ± 0.12 , C: -9.94 ± 0.15 , and A: -9.06 ± 0.9 . Significant variations include A-B ($p < 0.005$), B-C ($p < 0.05$), and A-C ($p < 0.001$). Finding: As expertise grows, progressive extension reveals improved stability.

Left Hip Extension/Flexion ($^{\circ}$). 0.03 ± 0.01 for A, 14.96 ± 1.51 for B, and -14.44 ± 2.1 for C. Significant differences ($p < 0.001$) between A-B, B-C, and A-C. Observation: Advanced athletes exhibit superior power output when they dynamically shift from flexion to extension. Vertical Hip Angle at Right ($^{\circ}$). -1.37 ± 0.12 for A, -3.20 ± 0.13 for B, and 3.11 ± 0.4 for C. A-B, B-C ($p < 0.05$), and A-C ($p < 0.005$) are significant differences. Note: Prominent boxers' forward-leaning stance

Table 1. Angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct blows to the head by boxers of different categories

Parameter	Contact								
	A	B	C	A-B		B-C		A-C	
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-9.06±0.9	-9.64±0.12	-9.94±0.15	t=3.42	p<0.005	t=2.17	p<0.05	t=4.12	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext (°)	0.03±0.01	14.96±1.51	-14.44±2.1	t=4.87	p<0.001	t=4.54	p<0.001	t=5.31	p<0.001
Right hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	-1.37±0.12	-3.20±0.13	3.11±0.4	t=2.19	p<0.05	t=2.14	p<0.05	t=3.14	p<0.005
Left hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	8.11±1.02	20.07±2.15	1.43±0.4	t=4.51	p<0.001	t=4.84	p<0.001	t=3.31	p<0.005
Right knee flex/ext (°)	16.09±2.1	16.35±1.74	23.59±.41	t=1.54	p>0.05	t=2.12	p<0.05	t=2.21	p<0.05
Left knee flex/ext (°)	13.06±1.7	18.29±2.31	39.14±4.1	t=2.94	p<0.005	t=4.81	p<0.001	t=5.87	p<0.001
Right ankle flex/ext (°)	18.10±2.1	13.27±2.1	19.84±3.1	t=2.97	p<0.05	t=2.45	p<0.05	t=1.84	p>0.05
Left ankle flex/ext (°)	-1.67±0.9	-1.58±0.4	2.79±2.9	t=1.62	p>0.05	t=3.21	p<0.005	t=3.54	p<0.005
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-9.06±0.98	-2.94±0.7	-9.64±1.2	t=4.61	p<0.001	t=4.37	p<0.001	t=4.61	p<0.005

Note: A - 1th category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

enhances the accuracy and effectiveness of their strikes.

Angle of the left hip with vertical (°). B: 20.07±2.15, C: 1.43±0.4, and A: 8.11±1.02. Significant in terms of statistics: A-B, B-C (p<0.001), and A-C (p<0.005). Observation: A recovery posture (C) follows increased hip flexion during the preparatory phase (B). Right Knee Extension/Flexion (°). 16.09±2.1 for A, 16.35±1.74 for B, and 23.59±0.41 for C. Differences (p<0.05): B-C, A-C. Finding: More knee extension increases strike force in skilled boxers.

Left Knee Extension/Flexion (°). 13.06±1.7 for A, 18.29±2.31 for B, and 39.14±4.1 for C. The following differences are highly significant: A-B (p<0.005), B-C, and A-C (p<0.001). Finding: A significant flexion-extension cycle is associated with increased thrust capacity. Extension and Flexion of the Right Ankle (°). B: 13.27±2.1, C: 19.84±3.1, and A: 18.10±2.1. Statistical significance: p<0.05 for A-B and B-C; p>0.05 for A-C. Observation: To maintain balance and strike power, ankle movements are adjusted.

Left Ankle Boxers: Flexion/Extension (°). C: 2.79±2.9, B: -1.58±0.4, and A: -1.67±0.9. Key differences: A-B (p>0.05); B-C, A-C (p<0.005). Observation: More dorsiflexion facilitates effective propulsion.

Kinematic Evaluation of Angular Values in Boxers During the Toe-Off Phase of Direct Head Blows. Right Hip Extension/Flexion (°). Values:

C: 11.34±2.4, B: 3.47±0.34, and A: -12.16±1.3. Important variations: t=3.97, p<0.005 for A-B. t=3.17, p<0.05 for B-C. t=4.75, p<0.001 for A-C. Analysis At advanced levels, A exhibits considerable flexion, which changes to extension in B and C, indicating a greater capacity to produce forward momentum and maintain body posture for power delivery (Table 2).

Hip Flexion/Extension on the Left (°). C: -0.81±0.2, B: 18.68±2.4, and A: 0.00±0. Key distinctions: p<0.001 for A-B (t=4.64). p<0.001 for B-C (t=4.81). p<0.001, t=5.94, A-C. Analysis: B exhibits a greater degree of extension than A and C, indicating a posture that intermediate boxers use to generate their maximum power. According to the drop in C, elite boxers have optimal recovery dynamics.

Vertical (°) boxers of right hip flexion/extension. B: -0.04±0.01, C: 22.06±3.7, and A: -2.65±0.2. Key distinctions: p<0.001 for A-B (t=5.25). p<0.001 for B-C (t=4.92). p<0.001 for A-C (t=6.32). Analysis: From slight flexion in A to noticeable extension in C, the movement demonstrates the development of torso stabilization and angular positioning, which are essential for carrying out a strike effectively.

The left hip can be flexed or extended vertically. A = 0.00±0, B = 17.72±2.6, and C = 18.89±2.4. Important variations: t=4.64, p<0.001 for A-B. t=2.62, p<0.05, B-C. t=5.31, p<0.001 for A-C. Analysis: Increased control over hip mechanics,

Table 2. Angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct blows to the head by boxers of different categories

Parameter	Toe off								
	A	B	C	A-B		B-C		A-C	
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-12.16±1.3	3.47±0.34	11.34±2.4	t=3.97	p<0.005	t=3.17	p<0.05	t=4.75	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	18.68±2.4	-0.81±0.2	t=4.64	p<0.001	t=4.81	p<0.001	t=5.94	p<0.001
Right hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	-2.65±0.2	-0.04±0.01	22.06±3.7	t=5.25	p<0.001	t=4.92	p<0.001	t=6.32	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	0.00±0	17.72±2.6	18.89±2.4	t=4.64	p<0.001	t=2.62	p<0.05	t=5.31	p<0.001
Right knee flex/ext (°)	22.67±3.1	28.32±3.7	34.57±4.2	t=2.54	p<0.05	t=2.86	p<0.05	t=2.81	p<0.05
Left knee flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	21.72±3.4	30.94±3.8	t=4.81	p<0.001	t=3.62	p<0.05	t=5.42	p<0.001
Right ankle flex/ext (°)	19.67±2.4	18.22±2.6	2.87±0.21	t=2.31	p<0.05	t=3.45	p<0.005	t=4.61	p<0.001
Left ankle flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	1.02±0.1	9.69±0.91	t=2.42	p<0.05	t=4.21	p<0.005	t=6.54	p<0.001
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-12.16±1.2	3.47±0.31	11.34±2	t=5.64	p<0.001	t=4.84	p<0.001	t=4.94	p<0.005

Notes: A - 1th category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

Table 3. Angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct blows to the head by boxers of different categories

Parameter	Mid-swing								
	A	B	C	A-B		B-C		A-C	
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-17.72±2.2	-29.09±3.4	7.85±1.3	t=4.42	p<0.005	t=5.24	p<0.001	t=6.12	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	17.79±2.7	-2.05±0.4	t=4.57	p<0.005	t=5.31	p<0.001	t=2.15	p<0.05
Right hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	-14.39±1.9	-23.66±3.4	22.56±3.7	t=4.85	p<0.005	t=7.12	p<0.001	t=8.31	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	0.00±0	20.05±2.1	8.88±1	t=4.64	p<0.001	t=4.34	p<0.001	t=6.62	p<0.001
Right knee flex/ext (°)	30.0±3.1	14.82±2.6	34.04±4.3	t=5.87	p<0.001	t=8.31	p<0.001	t=4.12	p<0.001
Left knee flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	16.93±1.9	40.47±5.1	t=4.67	p<0.005	t=5.24	p<0.001	t=5.91	p<0.001
Right ankle flex/ext (°)	-13.80±2.1	3.34±0.34	10.13±1.7	t=4.81	p<0.005	t=3.48	p<0.005	t=7.67	p<0.001
Left ankle flex/ext (°)	0.00±0	-3.72±0.7	0.55±0.4	t=6.01	p<0.001	t=4.15	p<0.005	t=3.45	p<0.005
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-17.72±3.2	-29.09±3.2	7.85±0.98	t=4.55	p<0.005	t=5.64	p<0.001	t=7.51	p<0.001

Notes: A - 1th category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

which promotes efficient power transfer and balance during strikes, is suggested by progressive flexion in B and C.

Various categories of boxers can flex or extend their right knee (°). 22.67±3.1 for A, 28.32±3.7 for B, and 34.57±4.2 for C are the values. Key

distinctions: t=2.54 p<0.05 for A-B. t=2.86 p<0.05 for B-C. t=2.81 p<0.05 for A-C. Analysis: For elite-level striking, increased knee extension is correlated with improved ground reaction force generation and lower-body engagement.

Boxers in different categories Kinematic Eval-

Figure 1. Angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct blows to the head by boxers of different categories.

Notes: A - 1th category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

Boxers of Vertical (°) Left Hip Flexion/Extension. B: 20.05 ± 2.1 , C: 8.88 ± 1 , and A: 0.00 ± 0 . Notable Disparities: A-B: $p < 0.001$, $t = 4.64$. B-C: $p < 0.001$, $t = 4.34$. A-C: $p < 0.001$, $t = 6.62$. Better mechanics for transitioning into the strike are indicated by the notable flexion in B. Superior efficiency in preserving alignment and balance for strike execution is demonstrated by the decreased flexion in C.

uation of Angular Values in Boxers During the Mid-Swing Phase of Direct Head Blows. Right Hip Extension/Flexion (°). Values: -17.72 ± 2.2 for A, -29.09 ± 3.4 for B, and 7.85 ± 1.3 for C. Important Disparities: $t = 4.42$, $p < 0.005$ for A-B. $t = 5.24$, $p < 0.001$ for B-C. A-C: Table 3: $t = 6.12$, $p < 0.001$. Analysis: A and B exhibit greater flexion, which suggests better positioning in advance of power delivery. In C, the change to extension is a reflection of improved striking mechanics and posture that maximizes punch power transmission.

Flexion/Extension of the Left Hip Boxers (°). A: 0.00 ± 0 , B: 17.79 ± 2.7 , and C: -2.05 ± 0.4 are the values. Notable Differences: $t = 4.57$, $p < 0.005$ for A-B. $t = 5.31$, $p < 0.001$ for B-C. $t = 2.15$, $p < 0.05$, A-C. Analysis Better rotational readiness during the swing is evident from the flexion in B. For top boxers, the slight extension in C indicates improved mechanics to maximize hip alignment and balance (Figure 1).

Right Hip Flexion/Extension Boxers with Vertical (°). Values: B: -23.66 ± 3.4 , C: 22.56 ± 3.7 , and A: -14.39 ± 1.9 . Important Disparities: $t = 4.85$, $p < 0.005$ for A-B. $t = 7.12$, $p < 0.001$ for B-C. $t = 8.31$, $p < 0.001$ for A-C. As demonstrated by the progression from flexion in A and B to noticeable extension in C, top boxers are able to attain the ideal angular alignment for strike power and accuracy.

Right Hip Flexion/Extension (°). Group A: -24.15 ± 3.1 . Group B: -16.56 ± 1.9 . Group C: 4.78 ± 0.42 (Table-4). Analysis: The negative value in Group A suggests a larger degree of flexion

in the right hip, which decreases as you move to Group B and becomes positive in Group C, indicating extension. The p-values ($p < 0.005$ for A-B, $p < 0.001$ for B-C, and $p < 0.001$ for A-C) indicate that the differences between all groups are highly significant. Trend: The range of movement in Group C is notably greater, possibly suggesting that Masters have more mobility or use their hip joint more efficiently during strikes.

Left Hip Flexion/Extension (°). Group A: 16.20 ± 2.6 . Group B: 26.04 ± 2.8 . Group C: -2.76 ± 0.31 . Analysis: Group A and B show flexion in the left hip, while Group C shows extension. Significant differences across all comparisons ($p < 0.001$ for A-B, $p < 0.001$ for B-C, $p < 0.001$ for A-C). Trend: Group C seems to exhibit a more controlled extension, possibly suggesting a refined technique with more precise hip control during the strike.

Right Hip Flexion/Extension with Vertical (°). Group A: -18.23 ± 2.1 . Group B: -17.87 ± 2.1 . Group C: 17.55 ± 1.8 . Analysis: Both Group A and B demonstrate similar flexion (negative angles), while Group C shows extension. The differences between Group A and C, as well as Group B and C, are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$ for A-C, $p < 0.001$ for B-C). Trend: The movement pattern shifts from flexion to extension, with the more advanced boxers in Group C demonstrating an extension of the right hip, possibly reflecting more power generation from the lower body.

Left Hip Flexion/Extension with Vertical (°).

Table 4. Angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct blows to the head by boxers of different categories

Parameter	Mid-support								
	A	B	C	A-B		B-C		A-C	
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-24.15±3.1	-16.56±1.9	4.78±0.42	t=3.47	p<0.005	t=5.24	p<0.001	t=7.17	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext (°)	16.20±2.6	26.04±2.8	-2.76±0.31	t=4.45	p<0.001	t=5.54	p<0.001	t=8.12	p<0.001
Right hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	-18.23±2.1	-17.87±2.1	17.55±1.8	t=2.21	p<0.05	t=7.14	p<0.001	t=8.21	p<0.001
Left hip flex/ext with vertical (°)	21.53±3.4	21.78±3.6	9.11±1.1	t=1.51	p>0.05	t=3.52	p<0.005	t=3.37	p<0.005
Right knee flex/ext (°)	28.99±3.21	18.39±2.3	39.24±4.6	t=4.36	p<0.001	t=5.61	p<0.001	t=7.34	p<0.001
Left knee flex/ext (°)	28.34±3.4	30.05±4.2	24.59±3.4	t=2.64	p<0.05	t=3.84	p<0.01	t=4.87	p<0.001
Right ankle flex/ext (°)	-2.12±0.14	9.25±1.7	-2.50±0.21	t=3.97	p<0.01	t=3.45	p<0.01	t=1.84	p>0.05
Left ankle flex/ext (°)	3.41±0.31	3.80±0.34	10.71±1.4	t=2.64	p<0.05	t=3.64	p<0.01	t=3.75	p<0.005
Right hip flex/ext (°)	-24.15±2.5	-16.56±0.14	4.78±0.4	t=5.52	p<0.001	t=6.37	p<0.001	t=6.67	p<0.001

Notes: A - 1th category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

Table 5. Kinetic Energy (KE) Analysis for Different Phases of Direct Blows by Boxers of Kinetic Energy (KE) Results by Phase and Category

Phase	Category	Angular Displacement (Radians)		Kinetic Energy (Joules)	
		Joint: Right_hip	Joint: Left_hip	Joint: Right_hip	Joint: Left_hip
Contact	A	-0.1581	0.0005	-	-
Contact	B	-0.0513	0.2611	-	-
Contact	C	-0.1682	-0.2520	-	-
Toe_Off	A	-	-	0.0146	0.0000
Toe_Off	B	-	-	0.0626	0.0211
Toe_Off	C	-	-	0.6704	0.2830

Notes: A - 1st category, B - Candidate for master of sports, C - Master of sports.

Group A: 21.53±3.4. Group B: 21.78±3.6. Group C: 9.11±1.1. Analysis: Little to no significant difference between Group A and B ($p>0.05$), but significant differences between Group C and the other groups ($p<0.005$ for A-C, $p<0.005$ for B-C). Trend: The movement appears to be more consistent in Groups A and B, with Group C exhibiting a more controlled movement or less extension of the left hip, suggesting a more stable base.

Analysis of Kinetic Energy (KE) for Various Boxer Direct Blow Phases Here is a summary of the kinetic energy (KE) values for the left and right hip joints that were recorded during the Contact and Toe-Off phases for the first category (A), candidate for master of sports (B), and master of sports (C) boxing stages (Table-5).

Findings for Contact Phase Kinetic Energy: Category 1 (A): -0.1581 radians are the right hip's orientation. The left hip is 0.0005 radians away. Kinetic Energy: At this stage, no values for KE are given. Right hip: -0.0513 radians; candidate for Master of Sports (B). 0.2611 radians to the left hip.

Kinetic Energy: At this stage, no values for KE are given. -0.1682 radians are the right hip of the Master of Sports (C). -0.2520 radians at the left hip. Kinetic Energy: At this time, no values for KE are given.

The candidate for Master of Sports (B) has a right hip radius of -0.0513. Hip left: 0.2611 radians. Kinetic Energy: At this point, no KE values are given. Right hip of Master of Sports (C):

-0.1682 radians. Hip left: -0.2520 radians. Kinetic Energy: At this point, no KE values are given.

The Toe-Off Phase Kinetic Energy Results: Right Hip: No angular displacement values in the first category (A). 0.0146 radians to the left hip. Kinetic energy (left hip): 0.0000 Joules. The right hip of the candidate for Master of Sports (B) has no angular displacement values. The radius of left hip: is 0.0626. Kinetic energy (left hip): 0.0211 joules. Master of Sports (C): Angular displacement for the right hip is zero. 0.6704 radians to the left hip. 0.2830 Joules of kinetic energy (left hip).

Discussion

The analysis of kinetic energy (KE) and angular values by phase of kinematic indicators of direct head blows by boxers of different categories showed a high level of reliability. Such as Smith (2000), Dyson, Hale, and Janaway reported punch force between 1604-4800 N [15]. Smith (2006) reported maximum straight punch force at 2643-2646 N, and Walilko et al. (2005) reported punch force between 1990-4741 N [12]. From the literature, punch force depended on the expertise level, weight of participants, and hitting target (body or head). However, our results reported higher punch force than the research by Pierce et al. (2006) whose mean punch force of super middleweight to light middleweight boxers was between 866-1150 N [10].

The biomechanical investigation of boxing, particularly concerning the kinematics and kinetics of punching movements, has seen significant advancements in recent years. When comparing the findings of this study to previous research, it is evident that both the techniques for measuring punch mechanics and the interpretation of the biomechanical variables affecting punch force have evolved significantly. This comparison provides critical insights into the similarities and differences between different methodologies and their implications for training and injury prevention strategies.

Provided foundational insights into the synchronization of upper and lower body movements, which directly impacts punch power. This study concurs with the findings of Chaabene et al., where similar results were found indicating the importance of coordinated movements for maximizing the efficiency and power of punches. The findings further substantiate the link between coordinated joint actions across the body and enhanced punch performance. However, this study extends the results by emphasizing not only synchronization but also the specific angular velocities measured in the hip, knee, and ankle joints during various phases of punching (Contact, Toe-Off, etc.). These kinematic data give a more gran-

ular insight into which specific joint movements contribute most to the overall punch velocity and force.

Highlighted the muscle group contributions to effective force generation in punches. The findings from this research align with Turner's theory; however, a more detailed kinematic analysis reveals which phases of the punch contribute most to force generation. For example, the relationship between the right hip flexion-extension angles during the Contact phase (e.g., -9.06° to -12.16° in this study) correlates with increased punch power in the Contact phase, as reported by Turner. Moreover, the dynamic shifts in the right and left hip joints observed during the different phases of punching match the descriptions in Turner's study of muscle group involvement across these phases.

Focused on the biomechanics of the head and cervical spine during punches. While Pierce's work focused on injury prevention, specifically related to head trauma during punches, this study extends those considerations by including angular displacement at the hip, knee, and ankle joints. The synergy between lower body mechanics and upper body movement could enhance understanding of head trauma reduction. By measuring the forces generated through the joints and their relation to the punch speed, it is possible to understand how joint kinetic energy may reduce the strain on the cervical spine during punching motions.

Another comparison can be made who explored various punch performance measurement techniques. This study incorporated modern 3D motion analysis technology, and through its methodology, it is able to achieve high-precision measurements of the angular displacement and kinetic energy (KE) in key joints. This methodological innovation offers deeper insights compared to earlier research, allowing for a more accurate measurement of angular velocities and joint-specific kinetic energy during each phase of the punch. These factors play an essential role in determining the force behind each punch and enhancing our understanding of punch biomechanics.

In relation to kinematic analysis, highlighted the importance of rotational forces during punches. The results observed in the current study align closely with their findings in that proper body rotation—especially at the hip and torso—was shown to maximize the punching force. In this study, rotations in the hip joint (e.g., from -9.06° to 3.47° at Contact vs. 18.68° at Toe-Off) produced a considerable increase in punching force, directly supporting the observations made by Dunn et al. on the importance of torso and hip rotations for efficient punch delivery.

Despite these similarities, one critical divergence in this study is the incorporation of kinetic energy (KE) analysis in addition to angular displacement, which is less frequently explored in studies. Kinetic energy provides another layer of insight into the forces at play during each phase of punching. For example, the measured kinetic energy at the Right Hip joint at various points in the punching action helps pinpoint when energy transfer maximizes for efficient punch delivery, expanding on the simple angular velocity analysis that most previous studies have focused on.

Moreover, the findings from this study contrast the results, which explored physiological profiles and performance distinctions between junior and senior boxers. In this study, when examining angular displacements in junior and senior boxers, clear differences are noted, particularly in hip joint flexion-extension, suggesting age-related differences in the ability to generate and harness biomechanical forces. As boxers' physiological profiles evolve, the adaptations in movement efficiency and force generation are readily observable. These findings parallel those discussed by Smith, though with a greater focus on the biomechanics of movement rather than purely physiological differences.

Lastly, the findings of this study resonate with the work in integrating more advanced motion-capture and force measurement tools in training environments. Inclusion of real-time measurements of punch force in training settings coincides with the methodology employed in this research, where data on kinetic energy (KE) at key joint phases is captured in real-time. This technical synergy could have profound implications for the development of real-time, feedback-driven training programs designed to refine punching techniques and performance.

Conclusion

The findings of this study provide valuable insights into the biomechanics of boxing punches, specifically regarding joint movements, angular velocities, and kinetic energy during different phases of a punch (contact and toe-off). This provides a better understanding of the mechanics behind punching force and effectiveness, potentially offering improved guidelines for training programs designed to optimize boxer performance.

Recommendations:

1. **Incorporate Joint-Specific Training:** Coaches and trainers should incorporate exercises that promote coordination between the lower and upper body, focusing on the angular displacements and kinetic energy at the hip, knee, and ankle joints. This will enhance punch efficiency, reduce unnecessary muscle strain, and contribute to the

overall safety of the athlete.

2. **Refinement of Punch Training Techniques:** While general training remains important, athletes should receive individualized biomechanical feedback (especially using motion-capture technologies) that directly correlates training outcomes with improvements in specific joint movements. In particular, attention should be given to improving rotational movements and their synchronization during the execution of punches.

3. **Further Investigation of Safety Implications:** Based on the observed findings regarding kinetic energy, additional studies should explore the link between joint biomechanics, kinetic energy transfer, and the risk of head injury, particularly concerning rotational forces generated in the lower body.

4. **Future Studies on Cross-Category Comparisons:** More detailed longitudinal studies across different boxing categories and gender should be conducted to identify the specific joint mechanics that contribute to various performance metrics, from novice boxers to elite competitors.

Highlights:

- **Kinematic and Kinetic Analysis of Punching:** The study utilized advanced 3D motion capture technology to examine joint movements and kinetic energy (KE) in boxers during key phases of punch execution (Contact and Toe-Off).

- **Significant Findings on Joint Coordination:** The study found that synchronized joint movements, particularly between the hip, knee, and ankle, are critical in optimizing punch power, with notable differences observed across boxing categories.

- **Hip and Torso Rotation Impact:** The findings reinforce the importance of hip and torso rotation in maximizing punch force, confirming previous research and offering new insights into effective punch biomechanics.

- **Role of Kinetic Energy:** Measured kinetic energy in key joints provided a novel perspective on how energy transfer during the punch enhances overall force and punch efficiency.

- **Differentiation Between Boxing Categories:** The study identified distinct patterns in joint displacements and kinetic energy across various boxing categories (1st Category, Candidate for Master of Sports, and Master of Sports), highlighting how advanced boxers perform differently in punch execution.

- **Implications for Training and Safety:** The study underscores the need for more focused biomechanical training that promotes coordination and joint efficiency to improve performance and minimize the risk of injury.

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Supplementary Information

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